

THE ROLE OF PROJECT BASED LEARNING IN DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

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Annotation: English Language Teaching is one of the key subjects for language students and a long-lasting interest for language professionals. Nowadays the profession of a language teacher is becoming more and more prestigious. Our society is keen on studying foreign languages because it gives people, children first of all, a competitive educational and professional advantage. Language teaching has undergone amazing change in the last decades: from teacher-centered classrooms to individualized learning, from grammar-translation method to communicative approach and from the chalkboard to the Internet, we have come a long way. Methods of foreign language teaching as a science deals with teaching methodology that helps language practitioner make learners acquire the target language. The object of the science is the educational process, the process of teacher-student interaction, which includes teacher's activity, students' activity and classroom management.

Key words: teaching, role-play, graph, videos, games, linguistics, B1 level student, B2 level student, English, Communicative Language Teaching, communicator, method, methodology, Direct approach, reading approach Competence, communicative competence, project based learning,.

1 INTRODUCTION

The communicative approach to language teaching makes the teacher the facilitator. The interaction between student and teacher is paramount as well as collaborative learning language. This type of learning language uses techniques that help to convey the ideas, thoughts, feelings and information to reach others. The Communicative approach is the product of educators and linguists who felt dissatisfied with Grammar Translation and Audio-Lingual approaches. It was evident that students were not learning enough realistic language relevant to their lives. Being at a loss to communicate in the target culture learners did not know how to use appropriate social language, gestures or expressions. Authentic language use and classroom exchanges where students are engaged in real communication with one another have become quite popular since 1970s.

The article defines different project based tasks to teach a new language and changes the role of teachers in the classroom making them facilitator. Sometimes in language learning classrooms, teachers come across with difficulties.

In order to solve the problems, it has been searched and found effective project based tasks to develop communicative competence of B 2 level learners. Because of survey we have realized which method is more successful for teaching new language.

The aim of teaching a foreign language is fourfold. Firstly, teaching foreign languages has its unique practical value. Learners are supposed to have an effective command of the language in familiar

situations; to be effective communicators in social, cultural, educational spheres and in everyday situations. Secondly, the aim has an educational character as learners are supposed to get acquainted with a new culture and be involved into cross-cultural study. Thirdly, the aim is valuable from cultural point of view as learners are supposed to adopt an appropriate system of communication in a modern society, to show their positive attitude to the target language and traditions of the target culture, to be brought up as tolerant, hard-working, active, outgoing and helpful people. Fourthly, the aim has a developmental dimension, as learners are supposed to be able to provide problem solving activities, to develop their speech abilities (imitation, logic, phono-and intonation hearing, language guessing, etc.).

Project-based learning (PBL) is a student-centered pedagogy that involves a dynamic classroom approach in which it is believed that students acquire a deeper knowledge through active exploration of real-world challenges and problems. Students learn about a subject by working for an extended period of time to investigate and respond to a complex question, challenge, or problem. It is a style of active learning and inquiry-based learning. PBL contrasts with paper-based, rote memorization, or teacher-led instruction that presents established facts or portrays a smooth path to knowledge by instead posing questions, problems or scenarios.

2 METHODS

The need to learn foreign languages is almost as old as human history itself. The field of foreign language

teaching has undergone many fluctuations and dramatic shifts over the years. This is the field where fads and heroes have come and gone together with the changes in youth culture. So the sphere feels a great impact of time and society. The requirements of time and society dictate how to teach foreign languages as throughout history foreign language learning has always been an important practical concern. If a foreign language is so important for practical purposes the most favorable teaching approaches are those which encourage students using language in order to acquire it. If the society is not interested in practical implementation of language, then comes the time of analyzing it. Over the centuries, language teaching methodology has been vacillating between these two types of approaches: one which focuses on using a language; the other which focuses on analyzing it. At the beginning of the 20 th century, this distinctive pattern was observable in the shift from the analytical Grammar Translation Approach to the use-oriented Direct Method. Later the shift was connected with the rise of popularity of communicative approaches which emphasize language use over rules of language usage. Labeling this or that approach as good or bad is not fruitful. Success and effectiveness of different approaches or methods depend on whether they meet the requirements of time and society or not.

Historically the origin of modern language education has its roots in the study and teaching of Latin. 500 years ago Latin was the dominant language of education, commerce, religion and government in much of the Western world. But later, during the Renaissance period, Latin abandoned its role as a lingua franca, gradually becoming displaced as a language of spoken and written communication. Since that time Latin together with ancient Greek has become the formal object of instruction in schools and universities rather than the language of everyday communication. Otherwise the influence of the method of presentation of the dead language has been great. Actually from the 17 th up to 20 th century the study of classical Latin and analysis of its grammar was the model for foreign language study. We feel the influence even now in the practices of Grammar-Translation Method, which became firmly entrenched as a method of teaching aimed at analyzing a language rather than using it.

However, the swinging of the pendulum continued and by the end of the 19-th century the focus in language study shifted back to utility rather than analysis. An alternative method to propose was the Direct Method, other labels of which are Natural/ Conversational /Anti-grammatical method as its proponents (F. Gouin, E.B. de Sauze) were strongly opposed to teaching formal grammar, learning rules and

translation practice. They advocated development of oral skills and the primary role of a spoken word. At the beginning of the 20 th century, given the lack of teachers who were fluent in the target language, their endeavor was not quite successful and this led to the endorsement of the Reading approach to language teaching. It was the reaction to the impracticality of the Direct approach as at that period of time reading, not speaking was viewed as the most usable skill in foreign language. Reading comprehension is the only language skill emphasized within the Reading approach. Translation becomes once more a respectful classroom procedure, only the grammar useful for reading comprehension is taught, vocabulary is controlled first, then expanded.

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Language is one of the means of communication, the process by which people exchange information or express their thoughts and feelings. Real-life communication is always situational. It happens under certain conditions, at a particular time in a particular place and includes verbal (language) and non-verbal (eye contact, body language, gestures, mime, and face expression) medium.

Communicators' activity connected with the verbal medium of communication is called speech activity. Communicators or interlocutors involved in communication process (at least two) exchange their ideas in a certain situation, with a certain motive or reason why to start and/or continue communication,

choosing the appropriate channel of communication – spoken and/or written.

The first interlocutor has to initiate communication, to start it having some message in his/her mind. This message is produced either orally (as an utterance) or in a written form (as a text). If the production is oral, the sender of the message is the speaker, who has something to say/ask/inform another interlocutor. If the production is written, the sender of the message is the writer, who initiates communication via writing a letter, SMS, e-mail, note, article, etc. with the purpose of information, sharing ideas, conveying their thoughts, asking somebody about something. Both the speaker and the writer produce speech, thus the skills of speaking and writing are called productive. While producing the message they have in their mind, both the speaker and the writer have to encode it into some language code, in this sense the two initiators of communication may be called encoders.

The second interlocutor has to decode the message sent after receiving it, to react on something that was heard or read. He/she should share some common assumptions of the world with the sender (the same language code, appropriate level of language proficiency, acquaintance with cultural surroundings and the subject matter of the message, etc.) The receiver of the oral information is the listener, whereas a written text is received by the reader. Thus, listening and reading skills are called receptive [6; 34-38].

Modern methodology subscribes to the idea that message comprehension is as much active process as message sending. The receivers' job used to be considered a passive one, when the listener or the reader should only open their minds and let the meaning of the text comprehended pour in, in other words, they soak up the information given like a sponge. In reality the process is much more complicated. Not all the meaning in the text actually gets into the reader's / listener's mind.

Unfortunately, there is no guarantee that the receivers will understand everything they listen to or read as it depends on their experience, motivation, language competence on the one hand, and the senders' ability to be clearly understood, on the other.

Communication is a two-way process, which is based on the cooperative principle. Without cooperation, human interaction would be far more difficult and counterproductive. As phrased by Paul Grice, who introduced the principle, it states, "Make your contribution such as it is required, at the stage at which it occurs, by the accepted purpose or direction of the talk exchange in which you are engaged". The cooperative principle can be divided into four maxims,

called the Gricean maxims, which are the guidelines for how to communicate successfully. The presumptions state what we as listeners/readers can rely on and as speakers/writers exploit. The first maxim is the maxim of quality. It contains a demand to be truthful in your messages and responses and not to say anything for which you lack adequate evidence. The second is the maxim of quantity with its demand to make conversation/communication just as informative and clear as required, correlated with the current purposes of the exchange. The third principle is the maxim of relation.

The participant's contribution should be relevant to the interaction and indicate any way that it is not. The fourth principle is the maxim of manner. People should avoid obscurity and ambiguity in their communication, be clear understood, brief and orderly. In this way the communication will be interesting and memorable for the interlocutors [2; 12-19].

Language is for communication, it is interpersonal activity for developing creative thinking and personal interaction. The focus shifts from grammar and sentence formation to the use of language in context, both in linguistic context and its social or situational context [2; 62-68].

As to the theory of language learning, CLT is based on: cognitive code theory: learning is not simply the learning of habits but an active mental process, learner is responsible for using and learning a language; second language acquisition theory: emphasis on comprehensible input (language is acquired by understanding messages), language learning comes through using language communicatively (learning by doing); CLT advocates a holistic approach to language learning. True human learning is both cognitive and effective. This is termed whole person learning. One of the main challenges of the Communicative approach is to integrate the functions of a language (information retrieval, problem solving, and social exchanges) with the correct use of structures. The question is how to combine communicative fluency with formal accuracy. The main goal of CLT is to acquire and increase communicative competence, which means being able to understand and interpret messages, understand the social contexts where language is used, apply grammar rules, and employ strategies to keep communication from breaking down. According to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages competences are the sum of knowledge, skills and characteristics that allow a person to perform actions and communicative language competences are those which empower a person to act using specifically linguistic mean.

The approach focuses on skill integration idea and aims to develop procedures for the teaching of the four language skills that acknowledge the interdependence of language and communication. Skills are integrated from the beginning; a given activity might involve reading, speaking, listening, and also writing (this assumes the learners are educated and literate), the range of exercise types and activities compatible with a Communicative approach is unlimited. Learners are encouraged to be involved in such communicative processes as information sharing, negotiation of meaning, and interaction. W. Littlewood distinguished between functional communicative activities and social interaction activities as major activity types in CLT [18].

Teacher role in any classroom setting can hardly be exaggerated. In teacher-controlled classes teacher is dominant, he/she is the main authority and expert and mainly teacher performs the role of controller. But in CLT classes the teacher is the initiator of communication, who provides opportunities for interaction by selecting content and classroom activities based on learners' needs and interests. Therefore teacher plays a variety of roles. First of all he/she is a facilitator who facilitates the communication process, and very often—an independent participant within the learning-teaching group. Some other roles may be as an organizer of recourses and recourse him/herself, a guide within the classroom procedures and activities, a group process manager, needs analyst, etc.

Students' security is initially enhanced by using their native language. Attitude to use L1 is relevant to students' needs. Its use is occasional and cost-effective when necessary.

Attitude to errors in communicative classroom is tolerant; learners are encouraged to take risks. Errors and mistakes are treated in a non-threatening way and viewed as inevitable, natural steps in language learning. The more language practice, the fewer mistakes are made, practice makes perfect.

Materials used in CLT have the primary role of promoting communicative language use. Practitioners of communicative teaching view materials as a way of influencing the quality of classroom interaction and language use. Jack C. Richards and Theodore S. Rodgers speak about three kinds of materials currently used in communicative teaching and label them as text-based, task-based and realia. Under the first label numerous textbooks designed to direct and support CLT are meant [18].

Task-based materials contain tasks and activities for classroom interaction as different games, role plays, conversational situations, etc. Many proponents of CLT

have advocated the use of authentic, from life materials in the classroom. For example, newspapers, magazines, signs, notes, e-mails, advertisements, etc. designed not for educational purposes. A variety of communicative activities can be built around such language-based realia.

The approach possesses more advantages than disadvantages in language teaching. Creative atmosphere of mutual cooperation, variety of classroom interaction, focus on learners' needs, facilitative presentation of language items in meaningful context motivate learners and stimulate their language use. CLT appeals to those who seek a more humanistic approach to teaching, one in which the interactive process of communication receives priority [2; 23-28].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Later M. Canale and M. Swain's version of communicative competence (1980) was related more with the communicative approach application in language teaching [7; 72-78].

They included grammatical, sociolinguistic, strategic and discourse competences in their definition. M. Canale and M. Swain highlighted the importance of context, but somehow ignored the form (grammatical accuracy) in order to achieve the communicative function.

L.F. Bachman's model (1990) is a more current attempt to take forward the subdivision of communicative competence provided by M. Canale and M. Swain. He proposed the framework of Communicative Language Ability (CLA) that includes language competence, strategic competence and psychophysiological mechanisms.

The above mentioned versions of communicative competence indicate three stages of development of the idea how to facilitate mutual recognition of language proficiency in the situation when the language learnt has immediate practical application outside the classroom.

According to the modern point of view, all human competences contribute in one way or another to the language user's ability to communicate and may be regarded as aspects of communicative competence. Common European Framework of Reference for Languages presents a list of general human competences and communicative language competences. General human competences include declarative knowledge, skills and know-how, existential competence and ability to learn.

Sociolinguistic competence or sociocultural competence is the third major component of communicative competence. Sociolinguistic competences refer to the sociocultural conditions of language use as it is said in CEF. Through its sensitivity

to social conventions (rules of politeness, norms governing relations between generations, sexes, classes and social groups, linguistic codification of certain fundamental rituals in the functioning of a community), the sociolinguistic component strictly affects all language communication between representatives of different cultures, even though participants may often be unaware of its influence [18].

Generally, communicative competence is viewed as functional language proficiency which involves interaction between different people or between a person and a written or oral text and comprises linguistic (language/speech), pragmatic (discourse/strategic) and sociolinguistic/ sociocultural competences.

Developing Speaking Skills

One of the most important goals of teachers is to enable learners to use English for communication. According to many theories, There are some types of speaking performance that can help students to improve speaking skill (Brown, 2007). Speaking skill can be improved by games, role play, etc. Evidence shows that speaking should incorporate activities in a group work (Oradee, 2012).

Imitation

Students should pay attention to certain vowel sounds and intonations; next they should imitate correctly. Meanwhile learners need to practice an intonation contour or to find exactly certain vowel sound.

Responsive

It refers to short replies to teachers. It can be learners to initiated questions or comments. Students should be active in the classroom. They should reply to teachers' questions and comments. They should participate in the classroom. For example:

T: *How's it going?*

S: *Pretty good!*

Intensive

Any speaking performance is planned to practice some phonological or grammatical features of language that can be self-initiated or pair work activity (Brown, 2007).

Transactional Dialogue

It is used to convey a message or exchange the information. In addition, it is utilized to elaborate a concept or to manifest the purpose of something. Learners should participate in conversation (Brown, 2007). For example:

T: *What is the main idea in this essay?*

S: *The I should have more power.*

T: *What do you mean?*

S: *Well, for example the I should have the power to gain my goals.*

Interpersonal Dialogue

It is regarded as maintaining social relationships not for transmission of facts and information involves factors like: casual register, colloquial language, slang, ellipsis, sarcasm and a covert "agenda" (Brown, 2007). For example:

Carol: *Hi, Tom, How's it going?*

Tom: *Oh, not bad.*

Carol: *Not a great weekend, huh?*

Tom: *Well, I'm really miffed about last week.*

Extensive

It refers to students at intermediate to advanced levels that are asked to provide extensive monologues in the form of oral reports, summaries or short speech (Brown, 2007). In order to improve second language skills, learners should practice regularly. First learners should expand their general vocabulary and then they can improve their domain of vocabulary by listening from simple sentences to complex sentences. Meanwhile they can increase their knowledge by reading short story and sometimes memorizing some important parts of it (Chastain, 1988). When you read a book, story and magazine aloud, it can help you more. When you practice, your fluency would be better, too (Celce-Murica, 2001). According to Hedge the term fluency has two meanings: The first, which is the ability to link unit of speech together with facility and without strain or in opportunities slowness undue hesitation and purpose a second, more holistic sense of fluency that of natural language use which is likely to take place when speaking activities focus on meaning and its negotiation when speaking strategies are used and when over correction is minimized. We should encourage students to take responsibility for their own learning; they should encounter with simple procedures. Another important factor is that the learners should participate in conversation by setting up a group (Celce-Murica, 2001). The conversation between students and the teacher should be based on classroom observation data (Wenli, 2005). Some teachers have problems with students that do not participate in classroom and are always silent like Chinese and Japanese students. Teachers should provide students facilities to participate in group work, for example: use pictures, role play, etc. (Wenli, 2005). Some studies show that teachers should prepare suitable environment for students to facilitate learning process. Learners can boost speaking fluency through "partner taping". Partner taping encourages students to stay in English while taping improves greater fluency and achieves extra practice outside of class and develop students' responsibility for their

learning. It also suggests simple practical “low tech” method of getting to improve more fluency in a foreign language and take responsibility for their language practice. It is for teacher to apply additional work in order to expand students’ English speaking ability

How Can Teachers Improve Students’ speaking skill and encourage them to speak more?

Teachers can use a funny discussion and ask students to talk about their best moments that they ever had. Students’ participation in discussion causes other students to actively take part in negotiation; therefore, students become surprised about their ability and intelligence (Celce-Murica, 2001). Some students have a lack of desire to speak because of their shyness and low confidence, but there is no appropriate solution about how teachers can overcome this problem.

Evidence shows that these learners should start with short answers, and short sentences, but it may be time-consuming. Teachers should use a lot of English speaking activities to motivate learners to study and speak in English, and they should increase learning classroom environment (Oradee, 2012).

Role-play

According to Tatayama “role play is a part of activity derived by various approaches to languages” He also mentioned that it is vital to improve learners’ comprehension and production system and their ability would be cooperate socio-pragmatic and pragma-linguistic knowledge in interaction. Role-play is one of the methods that enable learners to improve a range of real life spoken language in the classroom (Cook, 2001). For example, a teacher chooses a conversation from a book and after repeating aloud with students, teacher asked some students to be volunteers in role-play. This activity can help students to overcome their shyness, fears and anxiety. Learners can listen and practice phrases that are used in speech acts (Celce-Murica). Additionally, role play, as defined by Livingstone (1983), is a classroom activity which gives the students the opportunity to practice the language they may need outside the classroom. It is a speaking activity which improves communicative competence and provides practice in contexts which simulate real-life experience. My learners of English are children who have limited oral ability in using English. Their oral contributions in class involve mainly repeating what the teacher says or answering the teacher’s questions. They have some knowledge of grammar and vocabulary but cannot use this in oral production. In this study I wanted to examine whether using role plays with these learners would improve their oral fluency in English.

Videos

Çakır (2006) found that video materials have improved due to increasing the quality of speaking ability. According to an investigation by Rice & Woodsmall, the video markedly raise learners’ lexical grammar. The effectiveness of video depends on students’ age and interest in specific context (Silverman & Hines, 2009).

Flashcards

As highlighted by Palka (1988) flashcards have significant effect not only for learning vocabulary but also for learning sentences structures, tenses and phrasal verbs. Meanwhile, Brown (2000) claims that learners usually cope with new words by flash cards and most learners try to use them to review it afterwards.

Graphs

Graphs “serve as representation of real observation and as analytic tools for detecting under lying patterns which in turn inform the observer and the learner about phenomena (the target) under investigation” Traditional views consider graphing as intelligence manifested in students’ minds (Lynch, 1992). Another way to improve learners’ presentation is to utilize videos, graphs and flash cards (Pesce, 2013). Also using flash cards has appropriate effects on young learners. Besides, using pictures has vital rules in learning grammars on learner speaking ability (Ghapanchi & Sabouri). There are a lot of chants for children and adults, make learners proficient in vocabulary and pronunciation. They tell story and draw some pictures for learner and tell them “now you do it”. The other technique is interview. The significant advantage of interviews is their flexibility. They can be long or short and useful for learners from beginning level to advanced level; with high aptitude and low aptitude learners. They can be considered as additional oral activities or subsequent writing task. Another important factor is pronunciation. Learners have problems to pronounce words fluently with native like pronunciation because of prosodic features: like intonation, stress and other phonological nuances (Richards & Renandya, 2002). Another factor that Celce-Murica (2001) mentioned is intonation. Intonation can help learners analyze and generalize the sentences to notice the stress timed. Moreover, Internet can provide broad resources for learners and even teachers. There are a lot of sites and CDs that can help learners to pronounce like native learners (Nunan, 1991). Knowing grammatical and semantic rules is not sufficient instruments for speaking. Learners must be familiar with the knowledge of how native speakers use the language in the context of well-organized interpersonal exchange, in which many factors interact. Thus, it is difficult for EFL learners, especially adults, to speak the target language fluently and appropriately

(Richards & Renandya, 2002). Wong (2006) postulates that speaking competence deals with speaking accuracy and fluency. Speaking accuracy demonstrates “the extent to which the language produced conforms to language norms” (Yuan & Ellis, 2003) under which the appropriate use of pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammar are subsumed. Speaking fluency pertains to the ability to produce the spoken language “without undue pausing or hesitation”. Speaking can be deemed as an indispensable tool for language teaching and learning since it can “facilitate language acquisition and development” (Goh, 2007), and it can be fruitful to learner’s academic accomplishment and professional success (Saunders & O’Brien, 2006).

CONCLUSION

Project-based learning emphasizes learning activities that are long-term, interdisciplinary and student-centered. Unlike traditional, teacher-led classroom activities, students often must organize their own work and manage their own time in a project-based class. Project-based instruction differs from traditional inquiry by its emphasis on students' collaborative or individual artifact construction to represent what is being learned.

Project-based learning also gives students the opportunity to explore problems and challenges that have real-world applications, increasing the possibility of long-term retention of skills and concepts

PBL often relies on learning groups, but not always. Student groups may determine their projects, and in so doing, they engage student voice by encouraging students to take full responsibility for their learning.

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